

URGENCY AND TECHNIQUES FOR USING THE QUIZZZ APPLICATION IN LEARNING OF ISLAMIC EDUCATION LESSONS

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Abstract: The development of learning technology is a development in independent learning in the digital era. It can even be said that the role of learning technology development of Islamic Education Lessons is related to the use of information and communication technology in this digital era is very high. The development of learning technology is an actor in e-learning in the learning process. The development of learning technology is one of the parties that plays a significant role in learning, and is a catalyst for learning in the digital era. Learning in the digital era cannot be separated from the use of technology or what is commonly called e-learning. Especially with the goal of independent learning, namely preparing students to face socio-cultural changes and technological developments. One way is to use the Quizizz application. Learning of Islamic Education Lessons with Quizizz is here to help teachers and students so that the learning process can take place and enjoyable learning experiences can be experienced when distance learning is carried out. Quizizz is a student engagement platform that allows teachers to conduct interactive lessons and quizzes with their students. Created interactive quizzes have up to 5 answer choices including the correct answer and can add an image to the background of the question. Quizizz can provide data and statistics about student performance results in real time. Quizizz can not only be done while studying in class, but can also be made up of questions for homework, so students can play it anytime and anywhere as long as it does not exceed the allotted time limit. This of course makes it easier for teachers to give assignments such as exercises or tests to students while continuing to supervise online and avoiding students who cheat in learning of Islamic Education Lessons.

Keywords: Urgency, Quizizz Application, Learning, Islamic Education Lessons

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Introduction

The understanding of educational technology is inseparable from the understanding of technology in general. Many people think that technology is just machines or tools, but technology has meaning as a process that increases added value. The definition of technology itself is very broad and varied. Technology is the systematic application of science or other knowledge in practical tasks. So, in other words, it can be explained that when we develop a product, discipline, procedures, tools and techniques that are put together to make an innovation is called technology. If this definition is applied in the world of education, educational technology is a systematic application of science and other knowledge in educational tasks (Deni, 2013: 106).

In the current era, learning activities have begun to shift from conventional methods to remote methods, either offline or online. Learning that is carried out online is a learning process

that utilizes network and communication technologies such as the internet. The application of online learning focuses on network access and mobile technology devices, such as laptops, smartphones and tablets to build access to information without space and time limitations. The order of implementing online learning is based on the application of information and communication technology in the three most important sectors, namely: 1) Learning Resources, 2) Learning Media, 3) Learning Evaluation. This is done on an ongoing basis to build skills and knowledge concepts that will be mastered by students when they reach the end of the learning process.

Relationships between students and their learning resources can be created through the Quizizz application, so that when distance learning takes place students can enjoy an interactive, collaborative and solutive learning atmosphere to increase the effectiveness of student learning outcomes. Many learning media have been presented, which can be applied by teachers, one of which is game-based learning media, of course it can also be used as a means of conveying material in the learning process, namely to measure students' understanding while getting the material that has been taught.

Getting to know Quizizz as an interactive learning media in the digital era is important for teachers to know. Realizing independent learning with the concept of differentiated learning certainly requires supporting media. One element of the dimensions of the Pancasila student profile is collaboration, in which teachers can collaborate with the media in the teaching and learning process. This is in line with the educational context conveyed by our Father of Education, namely Ki Hadjar Dewantara. The learning process in applying the material must be flexible according to the needs, characteristics and interests of students. That flexibility can be like making every home a school, everyone a teacher, and every activity a study.

Based on this, a learning process can come from all aspects and all lines. Not only fixated on the classroom, but every place or house must be used as a school or learning resource. This implies that a learning process can be done anywhere and learning resources are not limited. The focus of learning on the independent curriculum is enough to prioritize the learning needs of its students. Adjusting to the times, the characteristics of today's students are more literate towards technological developments. It is not surprising that the use of technology to optimize learning has begun to be widely used for education. One of the technologies that can be used by teachers as supporting media is Quizizz

Discussion of Theory

A. Understanding the Quizizz Application

The Quizizz application is a website for creating online interactive quiz games that can be accessed via the web or downloaded in the form of an application. Quizizz is usually used in classroom learning, which is used for learning evaluation, or can be accessed by students to answer practice questions in the form of fun quizzes. Using Quizizz is very easy, users are divided into 2 parts, namely the first is the host (question maker), the question maker is usually a teacher/instructor. The second is that there are *users* (students) who join (*join*) to answer questions that have been made by the teacher. Access given to users/students who join is only in the form of working on questions and answer choices that must be answered. While answering the user/student can see the score/value in the form of a percentage and the Quizizz application is used online.

B. Benefits, Strengths and Weaknesses of the Quizizz Application

1. Benefit Quizizz App

Quizizz itself, is an educational game application that is narrative and flexible in nature, besides being able to be used as a means of conveying material, Quizizz can also be used as an interesting and fun learning evaluation medium.

2. Excess Quizizz App

The advantages include:

- a. For teachers, it's easy to make questions, meaning questions that have been made by the teacher in the form of a question archive, all you have to do is move them (*copypaste*), avoid copy-pasting questions from other people, because maybe there are students who have seen them. This is usually when students already know the teacher is using Quizizz they will find out or search to see the various questions on Quizizz (teachers need to be creative - at least archive questions that have been made by themselves);
- b. Each student answers the question correctly, several points will appear in one question and also gets a ranking in answering the question;
- c. If the student answers the question incorrectly, the correct answer will appear;
- d. If you have finished taking the quiz, at the end of the quiz there will be a *Review Question display* to review the answers we have chosen; And
- e. In doing the quiz, each student gets a different list of questions from the other students because the quiz is made in the form of *Homework /PR* so that the list of questions is randomized and for each student, the questions that appear are different.

3. Disadvantages of the Quizizz App

Meanwhile, some shortcomings, among others:

- a. Students can open new tabs, meaning students can sign in with another account if students have two email accounts;
- b. Hard to control when students open new tabs;
- c. Students may be lowered in rank even though they have done/answered all the questions asked, this is due to the "time problem", meaning that the speed at which students work on the questions will get a large score thus affecting their ranking; And

It will be a problem if there are some students who are late to join.

Research Journal on Quizizz App

1. First Journal

Journal Name	Al-Ghazali: Jurnal Kajian Pendidikan Islam dan Studi Islam
Journal Publisher	STAI NU Purworejo

Publication Year	2020
Article Title	Penerapan aplikasi <i>Whatsapp</i> , <i>Google Form</i> , dan <i>Quizizz</i> dalam Pembelajaran PAI di Masa Pandemi Covid-19 di SMK Negeri 3 Purworejo
Writer	Masrur & Reza Rismawanti
Url Address	https://ejournal.stainupwr.ac.id/index.php/al_ghzali/article/view/194

The results of the journal review show that the existence of the Covid-19 pandemic has had an impact on various sectors of life, including the provision of educational services. For the continuity of the educational process and in the context of participating in breaking the chain of the spread of the Covid-19 virus, the implementation of learning at SMK Negeri 3 Purworejo is adjusted to the social distancing policy. Teaching and learning activities are carried out at each student's home and carried out through online media (*online*). This study aims to describe the implementation of Islamic Religious Education and Moral Education (PAIdBP) learning activities online, to describe the implementation of online PAIdBP knowledge assessment activities, and to determine the effectiveness of implementing online learning activities carried out in class XI Dressmaking at SMK Negeri 3 Purworejo. The PAIdBP learning implementation consists of four online activities. The *Whatsapps* application is used for class management, including to deliver announcements, provide subject matter, deliver and collect student assignments. Assessment of PAIdBP knowledge learning outcomes is carried out using the Google Form and Quizizz applications. From all online activities, the average PAIdBP knowledge score of students was 76.115 and the percentage of students who had exceeded the KKM was 74.135%. The minimum completeness criteria for PAIdBP knowledge set from SMK Negeri 3 Purworejo is 75, and the percentage of students who have exceeded the KKM is less than 75% so that it can be concluded that online PAIdBP learning in class XI Fashion Design at SMK Negeri 3 Purworejo which is implemented is still not effective enough.

2. Second Journal

Journal Name	Ta'dibuna: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam
Journal Publisher	Universitas Ibnu Khaldun Bogor
Publication Year	2021
Article Title	Pengaruh Aplikasi Quizizz PAI dalam Meningkatkan Minat Belajar Siswa pada Masa Pandemi Covid-19
Writer	Adelia Fadillah Purwianto & Eni Fariyatul Fahyuni
Url address	http://ejournal.uika-bogor.ac.id/index.php/TADIBUNA/article/view/5829

The results of the journal review are that, in its development, the existence of the Quizizz application is increasingly being used at various levels of education. The application contains cognitive, affective, and psychomotor aspects. Technically making quizzes using the Quizizz

application by the teacher is done in a way that is, quizzes are made with up to 4 answer choices including the correct answer and can also add images to the background of the question, background, and arrange the questions as desired. Innovations that combine quizzes with audio-visual will provide students with meaningful learning because the auditory channel is capable of processing words and the visual channel can be used for processing images, so the load between the two will be balanced and no channel is overloaded. Responding to the challenges of digital-based learning during the Covid-19 pandemic, research on the influence of the Quizizz application on students' learning interest needs to be carried out in order to obtain research results that can provide a new perspective on the use of learning media in the education sector. The research uses correlational quantitative research methods with data collection processes using questionnaires. Based on the data obtained, the Sig < Alpha Research value ($0.000 < 0.05$) means that the hypothesis is accepted. The hypothesis is accepted if the significance value is less than 0.05, meaning that variable X has an effect on variable Y. If the significance value is more than 0.05, it means that variable X has no effect on variable Y. The results of the linearity regression test found R Square 0.721. So that means the Quizizz application has an influence of 72.1% on student learning interest and 27.9% is influenced by other factors outside the X variable.

3. Third Journal

Journal Name	Bestari: Jurnal Studi Pendidikan Islam
Journal Publisher	Institut Agama Islam Darussalam (IAID)
Publication Year	2020
Article Title	Pengaruh Penggunaan Aplikasi Quizizz terhadap Efektivitas Pembelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam
Writer	Syifa Agestrisna Nuramanah, Cecep Darul Iwan & Selamat
Url address	https://www.riset-iaid.net/index.php/bestari/article/view/474

The results of the journal review are that, the selection with the Quizizz application aims to achieve an effective learning using technology and make students more able to think critically. And aims to achieve and see the effect of the effectiveness of learning using technology. And it is hoped that PAI learning materials can be easily understood and can increase the learning effectiveness of students. In the implementation of learning, students can learn science cognitively, learn to do based on experience, and learn to live in togetherness. The purpose of this research is to determine whether the use of the Quizizz application influences the effectiveness of PAI learning. Quantitative research is research that tests a theory by analyzing data using numeric or numbers to prove a data is correct. The quantitative research method is a research method that is an experimental approach, used to describe existing phenomena that are taking place at present or in the past. Using the hypothesis that was used since the beginning of the study, reducing data into numbers, evaluating validity using various procedures relying on statistical calculations.

In collecting the required information and data, the researcher uses one technique, namely: Questionnaire Technique (Questionnaire). Based on the results of the research and discussion that has been carried out in the previous chapter, the researcher can draw the following conclusions: 1.

The use of the Quizizz Application at SDN 3 Cisaga is classified as moderate . This is based on the mean obtained for variable X data (using the Quizizz application) which is 80.17, then when converted using the price conversion guidelines the mean is in the range of 75.86 to 84.46, with moderate qualifications. 2. The effectiveness of PAI learning at SDN 3 Cisaga is moderate. This is based on the mean obtained for variable Y data (Effectiveness of PAI learning), which is 83.75, then when converted with the price conversion guidelines the mean is in the range of 81.08 to 86.40, with moderate qualifications. 3. The use of the Quizizz application at SDN 3 Cisaga is moderate. This is based on the mean obtained for variable X data (using the Quizizz application) which is 80.17, then when converted using the price conversion guidelines the mean is in the range of 75.86 to 84.46, with moderate qualifications. The use of the Quizizz Application at SDN 3 Cisaga has an influence on the effectiveness of PAI learning at SDN 3 Cisaga. This is shown from the calculations that have been carried out by the researcher, from the calculation results obtained through a significant test of the correlation coefficient at a significance level of 5% obtained $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($8,132 > 2.003$) and a sig or probability value < 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$) , shows that statistically the use of the Quizizz application has a significant effect on the effectiveness of PAI learning so that H_a is accepted and H_o is rejected. Thus the hypothesis which states that there is an influence between the use of the Quizizz Application on the effectiveness of PAI learning at SDN 3 Cisaga is declared accepted.

4. Fourth Journal

Journal Name	Jupendik : Jurnal Pendidikan
Journal Publisher	jupendik.or.id
Publication Year	2022
Article Title	Upaya Meningkatkan Motivasi Belajar Peserta Didik Melalui Aplikasi Quizizz pada Mata Pelajaran Pendidikan Agama Islam di SMA Negeri 1 Kupang
Writer	Suwarni Sulaiman
Url address	http://jupendik.or.id/index.php/jupendik/article/view/80

The results of the review of the journal are that, one of the stimuli that must be provided by the teacher is the use of the online game quizizz. Because this quizizz online game is also a learning game in the field of education, of course it relies on the material that has been provided so that children will be motivated to learn in the form of a game but the expected abilities can be assessed from the quizizz game. Motivation to learn contains efforts to achieve learning goals, namely understanding the material and developing learning. In addition, learning motivation is a driving force that makes someone interested in learning so that they will learn continuously. This research is a classroom action research *which* aims to motivate students in class XI IPS 1 at SMA Negeri 1 Kupang for the 2020/2021 academic year through action using the quizizz application. The research design used is an action research model design, in the form of a cycle. This research will be carried out in two cycles, and the steps of each cycle consist of planning, implementing, observing, and reflecting. Students' learning motivation is low in the Islamic Religious Education subject at Kupang 1 Public High School, one of which is because the learning media used by the

teacher is too monotonous and seems to be just the same so that student learning motivation decreases. In the midst of the spread of the Covid 19 Pandemic, it demands that we have to master information technology media, which is growing rapidly day by day. On the other hand, the development of science and technology, especially in the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 and entering the era of the 5.0 revolution, is expected to be a solution in the field of education. based on the assessment that has been carried out, the acquisition of an average value of student learning outcomes is 80.00 with a classical learning mastery of 85.19%. For affective learning outcomes, classical completeness is 85.19%.

5. Fifth Journal

Journal Name	PeTeKa: Jurnal Penelitian Tindakan Kelas dan Pengembangan Pembelajaran
Journal Publisher	Universitas Muhammadiyah Tapanuli Selatan
Publication Year	2022
Article Title	Penggunaan Media Pembelajaran Quiziz pada Mata Pelajaran PAI di Kelas VIII C SMPN 7 Karawang Barat
Writer	Bagus Kamajaya, Iwan Hermawan dan Kasja Eki Waluyo
Url address	http://jurnal.um-tapsel.ac.id/index.php/ptk/article/view/8132

The results of the journal review are that, in learning, teachers and staff as educators face many obstacles. One of the barriers to learning is that students do not show interest in learning when they study. As a teacher, I have to find different solutions to overcome these obstacles by using different learning media so that my students don't get bored. For example using the Quizizz application, the Quizizz application is an application used in carrying out online learning. Quizizz is a game-like app. Choosing this application as a learning medium that is integrated with teaching materials or assessment questions can make your lessons more interesting and fun. As the learning era develops, methods also need to be further developed. Don't just focus on one learning method. By changing the way we learn, teaching and learning activities become less monotonous and the material delivered to our students becomes more optimal. The method used in this research is the case study method. The data sources used were Class VIII C teachers at SMPN 7 West Karawang and three students. Data analysis by reducing data, presenting data, and drawing conclusions. Data collection techniques through observation, interviews and documentation. Here are the results of this research: There are two ways to access Quizizz. The first is for administrators (teachers) and the second is for participants (students). Especially administrators (teachers) who are required to get their Quizizz account before taking quizzes. An administrator (teacher) can access Quizizz at quizizz.com and a participant (student) can access Quizizz at join.quizizz.com. Both administrators (teachers) and participants (students) can sign up for Quizizz via email. There are also several supporting and inhibiting factors. The fact that students currently have an average mobile phone supports this to ensure students don't stutter about technology and can participate in learning using this quiz learning media. , the disincentive is that new students use this instructional medium in a way that initially makes them feel indifferent and therefore incomprehensible

Conclusion

Quizizz itself, is an educational game application that is narrative and flexible in nature, besides being able to be used as a means of conveying material, Quizizz can also be used, as an interesting and fun learning evaluation medium. Learning activities of Islamic Education Lessons at school or at home can certainly easily become boring activities for students. So, with the ease of access to learning media today, teachers can use, then develop evaluation media through the Quizizz application, so that they can achieve educational goals. Each learning media in its use has advantages and disadvantages in several ways, both technically and non-technically. In terms of the choice of using the Quizizz Web Tool, there are advantages and disadvantages that need to be paid attention to by teachers, namely technically this includes, among other things, related to the menus on Quizizz, non-technically for example related to the internet network. If we assume that all users have/are ready with their internet network, then there are several advantages of the Quizizz Web tool media as a tool for evaluating learning outcomes.

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